

CARRASCOZA, João Anzanello. **Vamos acordar o dia?** Histórias de uma linha só [Let's wake the day up? One-line stories]. São Paulo: SM, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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João Carrascoza defines the content of his book as early as the title: one-line stories. Loose words that inspire such stories with subtlety and poetry. Childhood curiosity and perception are expressed with impressive accuracy, as in “Noise: is it the bogeyman? No, only grandpa’s snores”. An award-winning author and masterful short story writer, Carrascoza won the Prêmio Literário Biblioteca Nacional in 2017 (for Young Adults Literature), as well as the Prêmio FNLIJ in 2018 (for Best Editorial Project).

Keywords: Poetry. Curiosity. Create.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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